
PERSONAL EXPOSURE AND HEALTH DATA PLATFORM TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Version: v1.0
Applies from 10/06/2026 to current

1. Personal Exposure and Health Data Platform Manager

VITO, Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek, Limited liability company organized and existing under the laws of Belgium (CBE 0244.195.916), with registered office at Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium, will act as the PEH Data Platform Manager, responsible for the overall coordination, governance, operation, and continuous development of the Personal Exposure and Health (PEH) Data Platform.

2. For Data Providers

By sharing information with the PEH Data Platform, I acknowledge as data provider that I have read, understood, and agree to abide by the following terms and conditions:

Single measurement data:

The single measurement data that I upload are processed in accordance to:

- The Protocol on the management and use of the Personal Exposure and Health Data Platform (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19232226>), or
- The Personal Exposure and Health Data Platform processor agreement (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20797188>)

The document that applies, depends on the use case:

- The Protocol on the management and use of the Personal Exposure and Health Data Platform applies to institutes that intend to enable access to single measurement data to stakeholders for at least one of their studies. Access to single measurement data by stakeholders is only enabled after explicit study-specific consent has been provided by the data provider and the institute has signed the Protocol.
- The PEH Data Platform processor agreement applies to institutes that object to enable stakeholder access to single measurement data. The aim of those users is to use the PEH Data Platform services, such as: data harmonisation, data validation, data enrichment (adding derived variables based on the uploaded data), and calculation of summary statistics. Since those services require processing of single measurement data, the Personal Exposure and Health Data Platform processor agreement is necessary.

Summary statistics:

The PEH Data Platform processes the single measurement data that I upload to summary statistics (i.e. aggregated data). By accepting PEH Data Platform Terms and conditions, I consent that:

- the PEH Data Platform will make the summary statistics of my study publicly available.
- the summary statistics will be made publicly available via third parties. These include, but may be not limited to:
 - IPCHEM (<https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu>)

Metadata:

The PEH Data Platform collects metadata information on the study from which I provide single measurement data. Those can be collected either separately from the single measurement data by requesting those data explicitly (e.g. project / study information) or processed from the single measurement data that I upload (e.g. measured compounds). By accepting PEH Data Platform Terms and conditions, I consent that:

- the PEH Data Platform will make the metadata of my study publicly available.
- the metadata will be made publicly available via third parties. These include, but may be not limited to:
 - IPCHEM(<https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu>)
 - Molgenis (<https://molgeniscatalogue.org/>)

Contact details:

By accepting the terms and conditions of the PEH Data Platform, I consent that my contact details as data provider (or any other contact details that I provide as contact point concerning the uploaded data) are processed by the PEH Data Platform Manager and may be shared with third parties (including, but not limited to IPCHEM and Molgenis), only when strictly necessary for the purpose of verifying, clarifying, or addressing any issues related to the data of my study and in the process of granting access to single measurement data. These contact details will not be used for any other purposes. Personal data are processed in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) and applicable Belgian data protection legislation.

Liability

The Data Provider remains solely responsible for the accuracy, completeness, legality, and quality of the uploaded data.
